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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Colibrì is a X-ray telescope which is currently in the concept study phase. The main objective of the Colibrì mission is to study the structure of accretion flows in the near vicinity of black holes and neutron stars and the study of emission from the surface of neutron stars. With high spectral and time resolution, and high throughput, Colibrì will allow the study of accretion disks and coronae, including reflection and re-emission of radiation by the disk, and observations of isolated and accreting neutron stars.

The Colibrì concept is based on multiple non-imaging X-ray collectors similar to NICER but with cryogenically cooled transition edge (TES) detectors for high energy resolution and sensitivity. Colibrì aims to achieve an energy resolution finer than 1eV at 2keV (3eV at 6keV), and count rates up to 100kHz, in an energy range of 0.1-10keV. The timing precision of Colibrì aims to be better than 1 micro-sec, matching the innermost orbital period for a 10 solar-mass black hole. The total effective area of Colibrì is to be at least 2000 cm² at 6.4keV.

The study began in fall 2018 represented by multiple academic and industry partners encompassing a large portion of the Canadian high energy astronomy community. Continued mission development will increase Canadian capabilities in a number of facets. Highly qualified personnel (HQP) would be trained by via science and instrumentation studies. Moving towards mission flight also allows for the retention of HQP in astronomy, the space industry, and related fields within Canada. As Colibrì will take advantage of TES detector technology, the team is collaborating with the Stewart Blusson Quantum Matter Institute in order to develop and build the detectors at UBC, building Canadian technical capabilities to produce sensors which are widely used in industry and scientific experiments. The continued development of the Colibrì mission would lead to the first Canadian-led flagship X-ray telescope.

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1 Key Science Goals

In the past 50 years, we have been able to observe what could be defined as the most amazing laboratories in the Universe: black holes and neutron stars. These objects, often called compact objects, uniquely present an environment to test the laws of physics at their extremes: the density in a neutron star reaches values several times higher than nuclear density, magnetic fields are billions of times higher than the Sun's, and gravity around black holes is so strong as to trap light itself. In this short period of time, we have learned a lot about compact objects, but their best kept secrets are still a mystery to us.

The X-ray emission of compact objects presents a rich phenomenology that can lead us to a better understanding of their nature and to address more general, yet fundamental physics questions:

- ◇ **Does general relativity (GR) apply in the strong gravity regime? Is the spacetime around black holes well described by the Kerr metric?**
- ◇ **Can we better understand the physics of accretion? How do accretion disks lose angular momentum? What is the mechanism behind winds? How are jets launched?**
- ◇ **How does matter behave in extreme environments in terms of density, gravity and magnetic fields? What is the physics of ultra-dense matter? What are the masses, radii and atmospheric composition of neutron stars?**

This white paper presents a newly proposed mission, *Colibrì*, which will be able to investigate these questions to a new level. The key characteristics of *Colibrì* are a combination of high-time resolution, high-spectral resolution and high throughput. Fig. 1 depicts the effective area of several mirror design choices for *Colibrì* where our baseline design, *Colibrì* f/15, is shown in purple.

Key science goals: Black Holes

Our science objectives include the study of accretion disk physics and the effects of strong-field gravity around black holes, as well as probing the spacetime around black holes and putting constraints on different theories of gravity. Specifically, we will achieve these objectives through the study of black hole reverberation and of quasi periodic oscillations in black-hole binaries:

- Black hole reverberation
- Quasi-periodic oscillations (QPOs)

Key science goals: Neutron Stars

We aim to study accreting and isolated neutron stars to understand the physics of accretion onto neutron stars and to measure important properties of neutron stars such as their mass, radius and atmospheric composition through high-time and high energy resolution spectroscopy:

- Neutron-star accretion disks
- High-spectral-resolution, high-throughput spectroscopy of the neutron star surface
- High-spectral-resolution, high-time-resolution spectroscopy of the neutron star surface

A companion white paper (E053: Caiazzo et al., “Unveiling the secrets of black holes and neutron stars with high-throughput, high-energy resolution X-ray spectroscopy”) outlines the key science cases for *Colibrì*, so we will focus on a few highlights here.

High-Energy Resolution, High-Throughput

Detecting absorption lines from neutron stars could reveal their surface chemical composition and physical conditions (e.g. surface gravity, pressure, temperature). Alas, high-spectral-resolution observations of neutron stars have not revealed verified atomic absorption lines yet. Recently however, the *Hitomi* X-ray satellite found the first

Figure 1: The effective collecting area of *Colibrì* compared to some recent and future X-ray missions.

evidence for weak and narrow absorption lines from the rotation-powered pulsar PSR J1833-1034 in the supernova remnant G21.5-0.9 (Aharonian et al., 2018) at 4.2345 keV and 9.296 keV. The observation is presented in the left panel of Fig. 3 in blue. The red and black points show the simulated results with *Colibrì*'s TES arrays coupled to collector optics. Depending on which line and on the configuration of the telescope, *Colibrì* would find two to ten times more photons within the line than *Hitomi*, with similar exposure time. Such an instrument would also open the possibility of phase-resolved spectroscopy to verify that the feature indeed originates from the pulsar rather than the surrounding nebula. PSR J1833-1034 rotates with a period of 66 ms, so the rotational velocity at the equator of the neutron star is about 1000 km/s, yielding a width of about 15 eV, just a factor of about three larger than *Hitomi*'s energy resolution. If the line indeed originates at the surface, it is somewhat surprising that *Hitomi* discovered such a narrow feature. RXTE found hints of absorption edges at about 7.5 keV during the cooling phases of X-ray burst. The right panel of Fig. 3 depicts a simulated observation by *Colibrì* of a neutron star cooling after an X-ray burst with an absorption edge of forty percent at 7.5 keV. The lower portion of the panel shows the residuals relative to a model without an edge. The presence, strength and location of the edge are clearly evident, yielding evidence of the nuclear reactions in the burst and possibly the gravitational redshift of the surface.

Searching for weak-line features in the spectra of AGN has uncovered several surprises in the past few years including fast outflows (Gupta et al., 2013; Cicone et al., 2018; Boissay-Malaquin et al., 2019) and evidence for warm-ionized gas between the galaxies, the so-called missing baryons (Nicastro et al., 2018; Kovács et al., 2019). *Colibrì*, with its wide energy coverage, high spectral resolution, and sensitivity, will excel in this regime. Fig. 2 shows that *Colibrì* will dramatically outperform *Hitomi* and its successor *XRISM/Resolve*, and it will be competitive with the much larger *ATHENA* mission, even exceeding *ATHENA*'s sensitivity to weak absorption lines above 4.5 keV, where the iron K- α lines lie. *Colibrì* has the potential to go beyond simply detecting the warm-hot ionized intergalactic medium: it will be able to characterize the properties of the missing baryons, including measuring metallicities to provide insight into how the material has been enriched with metals.

High-Time Resolution, High-Throughput

In black-hole binaries and AGNs, accretion to the central black hole takes place via a geometrically thin, optically thick accretion disk, which emits thermally in the low-energy X-rays for X-ray binaries and in the optical and UV bands for AGNs (Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973; Novikov & Thorne, 1973). The photons emitted by the disk are thought to be Compton up-scattered in an optically thin corona, which produces a power-law spectrum in the high-energy X-rays (Thorne & Price, 1975; Sunyaev & Truemper, 1979). Some of the up-scattered photons in the

Figure 2: Weak-line figure of merit for *Colibrì*, Athena and XRISM. The signal-to-noise of a weak line is proportional to $\sqrt{A_{\text{eff}} t_{\text{obs}} / \Delta E}$.

corona are reflected back into the line of sight by the disk. This reflection emission presents particular features, that include an iron $K\alpha$ fluorescence line at 6.4 keV and a reflection hump that peaks at ~ 30 keV (Ross & Fabian, 2005; García et al., 2013). The coronal emission shows rapid aperiodic variability, on timescales of milliseconds for stellar mass black holes and of minutes for AGNs. Neutron stars also accrete via a disk, but in addition, the material accreted onto the surface causes repeating thermonuclear reactions that are observed as bright bursts of X-ray emission, with timescales that go from 100 ms to several hours (Belian et al., 1976; Grindlay et al., 1976; Woosley & Taam, 1976; Maraschi & Cavaliere, 1977; Cornelisse et al., 2003; Cumming et al., 2006; Galloway et al., 2008; Keek & in't Zand, 2008). Similar to the coronal emission for black holes, this X-ray-burst emission can be reflected by the accretion disk, and indeed reflection spectra have been observed (Ballantyne & Strohmayer, 2004; Cackett et al., 2010; Keek et al., 2017, 2018).

With a fine enough timing resolution, the reflected emission can be used to map the inner region of the accretion disk. The variability in the coronal emission, or in the X-ray bursts, gets reflected in the reverberation signal with a light-crossing time delay (Uttley et al., 2014), with time delays of the order of a few hundreds of microseconds for Galactic binaries, and much longer for AGNs (scaling as $\propto M$). Also, as different parts of the accretion disk will be illuminated in subsequent times, photons of different energies will present different time delays, reflecting the characteristic Doppler shift of the reflection region. Such reverberation lags have been detected in several AGNs with *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* (Zoghbi et al., 2012; Kara et al., 2016), and very recently in the X-ray binary MAXI J1820+070 with *NICER* (Kara et al., 2019).

The high-throughput and high-time-resolution of *Colibrì* will open a new window on probing the inner region of accretion disks where relatively short observations (1 ks) can not only measure the lag timescale but also recover the response function directly as shown in Fig. 4. The width of the recovered response is inversely proportional to the count rate, so effective area and bright sources are crucial to resolve the response on short timescales. Although the level of noise in the measured response depends on the exposure time or the fraction of reflected radiation, the recovered width of the response function is independent of these parameters; therefore, a long-duration observation can be split into small time intervals or small energy intervals to measure how the response function changes with time as done by (Kara et al., 2019), or, if it does not change significantly, to measure it in detail as a function of energy as proposed by (Mastroserio et al., 2018). The right panel of Fig. 4 depicts this scenario, where we have examined the response for just a narrow range of energy (10^{-3}) in blue over a one kilosecond observation. The orange curve gives the original ten-percent reflection case. Although the signal for the narrow energy range is

Figure 3: Left: Simulations of the lines detected with *Hitomi* (blue) from PSR J1833–1034 for *Colibrì* for the same observing time with two mirror configurations: single-bounce collector (black) with three times the geometric area of *NICER* and double-bounce collector (red) with the same geometric area as *NICER*. Right: Simulated observation with *Colibrì* during the cooling tail of a X-ray burst exhibiting an absorption edge at 7.5 keV.

noisy, the underlying response remains apparent even for a short observation time.

2 Technical Overview

The key characteristics of *Colibrì* are its high spectral resolution, high throughput and large effective area, and they can all be achieved by using already mature technologies: thin-foil nested X-ray mirrors and transition-edge sensors (TES) as single-photon X-ray bolometers. Please consult Tab. 1 for an overview of the mission parameters. An array of seven telescopes yields a total effective area slightly larger than the three *XMM-Newton* telescopes with a focal length of 4.9-metres (see Fig. 5). The reduced focal length is achieved by reducing the outer diameter of each telescope to 32 cm (compared to the 70 cm for *XMM-Newton*) and by optimizing the on-axis performance at the expense of performance off-axis. This results in a large effective area for high-resolution spectroscopy from 0.2 keV to 20 keV as shown in Fig. 6 on the left. *Colibrì* offers a similar energy resolution to the gratings on *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton* and to the bolometers on *Hitomi*'s SXS, but with ten times the effective area of these missions. It gives a similar energy resolution to *ATHENA* with lower effective area below about 6 keV, but higher above 6 keV, because of the mirror-design choices.

The second key characteristic of *Colibrì* is high throughput combined with high-time resolution. The optics are purposefully defocused so that the emission from a source on-axis is spread over a large portion of a TES array. Furthermore, seven arrays operate in parallel. This dramatically reduces the likelihood of several photons landing on the same detector element within a short time, which would result in poor energy measurements, pile-up and lost photons, and allows to sustain count rates a factor of 1,000 larger than *ATHENA*. Furthermore, because the individual detector elements relax more quickly than those planned for *ATHENA*, and there are seven arrays operating in parallel, *Colibrì* will over-perform *ATHENA* by more than a factor of ten in count rate even if *ATHENA* offers a defocused observing mode. *Colibrì*'s rapid sampling of the TES arrays will achieve a time resolution similar to that of *NICER* and a factor of one-hundred finer than *ATHENA*. Fig. 6 on the right, depicts a summary of past, current and planned missions in the X-ray-timing space.

3 Technology Drivers

At its heart, *Colibrì* relies on TES-enabled X-ray bolometers with small relaxation times and high sampling rates. These detectors, combined with non-focusing optics, yield high throughput, high spectral and timing resolution and high quantum efficiency over a wide range of photon energies. The performance that is required for *Colibrì*'s

Figure 4: Simulations of *Colibrì* observations of the reverberation response of Cygnus X-1 with a 1 ks *Colibrì* observation of a bright X-ray source with 100,000 photons per second where a fraction are reflected with a fixed delay. In both panels, the green shows the input response including windowing effects. The left panel shows the case where 10% are reflected with 5 ms delay with blue depicting the directly deconvolved and orange showing the Weiner deconvolved response. In the right panel, only 0.1% (blue) or 10% (orange) of the photons are reflected with a 50 ms delay. In this panel both response functions are obtained with Weiner deconvolution.

Figure 5: Cut-away of *Colibrì* to highlight the optical path, detectors and cooling concept.

bolometers has already been achieved in the laboratory, and similar detectors are already in use at X-ray beamlines. *Colibrì* could be the first mission to use these detectors in space. Although *Colibrì* requires a cryogenic focal plane, the individual detector arrays and the accompanying superconducting electronics are much smaller than the focal planes of recent CMB experiments (e.g. Planck HFI at 100 mK) that have required similar operating temperatures; *Hitomi*'s SXS used a similar technology as *Colibrì*, and operated also at 50-100 mK. Furthermore the X-ray optics are well tested; telescopes with similar or better performances have been used on many missions.

The first key technology challenge is the on-board pulse processing that is required to achieve the energy and time resolution. Each of nearly two thousand TES bolometers must be sampled every 5 microseconds, for a total sampling rate of 400 MHz. We have developed a scheme of linear filters to achieve the required energy and time-resolution that will limit the required on-board computation to a manageable level. For example, *Hitomi*'s SXS pulse processor was limited to count rates below 200 Hz by computational constraints. We plan to achieve counts of 100s of kHz from sources with Crab-like fluxes.

The second key challenge is to bring the data back to the ground. During a day-long observation of a bright source, *Colibrì* will amass about 50 GB of data (assuming just five bytes per photon), twenty times the mean rate for HST and one-fifth that of JWST. However, with *Colibrì* in low-Earth orbit, the time each day to downlink data to a single ground station is dramatically diminished. We are exploring three options: a high-frequency (e.g. Ka-band

Table 1: Key Mission Parameters

Baseline requirements		Optics	
Energy range	0.5-20 keV	Focal length	4.9 m
Spectral resolution	2-5 eV	Number of Arrays	7
Timing resolution	250 ns	Foils per Array	30
Effective area	3,000 cm ²	Inner Radius	4 cm
Count rate	>100 kHz	Outer Radius	24 cm
Orbit		Geometry	Conical Wolter I
Altitude	1,688 km	Coating	Iridium
Inclination	103.0°	Field of View	50 arcseconds
Period	120 minutes	Angular Resolution	6 arcseconds
Sun Synchronous		Detectors	TES Bolometers
Payload		Bath Temperature	70 mK
Size	2.1 m x 7.0 m	T_c	100 mK
Mass	2,000 kg (fixed bench)	Array	12 × 12 (50 μm pitch)
Power	1,800 W	Lifetime	minimum 5 years

Figure 6: Left: X-ray Missions with X-Ray Spectroscopy Figures of Merit: Effective area and Spectral resolution at 1 keV and 10 keV. Right: X-ray Missions with X-Ray timing figures of merit: time resolution and throughput.

Figure 7: Left: Energy resolution achieved with linear filters, $5.12 \mu\text{s}$ sampling, thermometer and Johnson–Nyquist noise. Right: TES array for X-ray detection from Lee et al. (2015). The collector optics focus X-rays to a spot on the order of one millimeter in extent, hence the TES array will highly oversample the PSF to achieve high throughput.

as for JWST) downlink to a single ground station, downlink via satellites in high Earth orbit (as for Hubble) and an optical downlink to a telescope ground station. The final option potentially offers the most flexibility and room for growth but also is the most technically challenging.

The total power requirement for cooling the focal plane is about 1600 Watts. Although we do not yet have power estimates for other systems, cooling will play a major part of the power budget for the mission.

4 Organization, Partnerships, and Current Status

The *Colibrì* collaboration consists of most of the Canadian high-energy astrophysics community teamed up with Canadian particle and condensed matter physicists as well as other scientists around the world. We are in the midst of an 18-month science concept study funded by the Canadian Space Agency, with Honeywell and MDA as industrial partners. The preliminary optical design and cooling concept are complete. The focus of the second half of the study is the further development of the science case and a detailed plan for the payload and spacecraft bus. The study will end in early 2020. We have identified several additional potential partners: NASA (mirrors and TES detectors), NIST (TES detectors) and the Canadian Light Source (testing and calibration), NASA/ESA (launch).

5 Schedule

The proposed *Colibrì* mission is currently in a science concept study stage, to be concluded in early 2020. This stage will define the mission success criteria as well as the mission requirements. In an optimistic timeline, the mission definition phase will continue for 4 years. During this time, science maturation studies and technology development studies will proceed in parallel to the mission definition in order to increase the science and technology readiness levels.

Over the subsequent 6 years, activities leading to launch will include defining the system requirements, a preliminary system design and a detailed system design, and then fabricating, integrating and testing the system. A data analysis pipeline will also be developed. This will lead to a mission launch in about 10 years, in the early 2030's. After the commissioning activities, the nominal science operations are estimated to occur over 5 years. Decommissioning activities are estimated to take 2 additional years (ending in 2037) with the safe disposal of the *Colibrì* space mission and final data archiving with documentation to ensure the usefulness of *Colibrì* data long

after the mission is completed.

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1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The mission science goals are to understand the behaviour of matter with extreme densities and magnetic fields. Observations of black hole reverberation mapping and quasi-periodic oscillations will open a new window into understanding general relativity in the strong gravity regime as well as the physics of accretion. With the combined high-time and high-energy resolution spectroscopy of *Colibrì*, the observations of QPOs from neutron stars will help place constraints on their mass-radius relationship. There have also been hints of the presence of absorption lines in both accreting and isolated neutron stars—the nature of which remains a mystery. *Colibrì* will be able to robustly detect these features. The ability of *Colibrì* to resolve absorption features can facilitate understanding the topology of the magnetic fields of neutron stars, including magnetars.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main sources of scientific risk involve issues with the instrument which could lead to the science goals of the mission not being reached. In order to mitigate the negative effects of the background, instrumental defects and stray light, careful calibration of the PSF of each detector will be performed routinely throughout normal mission operations. The *Colibrì* design has 7 telescopes and the loss of the detectors/telescopes would lead to a graceful degradation of science return. For issues that arise due to cooling, there would be an impact on the energy resolution, but science could still be conducted. A single point of failure would be with malfunctions with the dewar containing coolant, careful testing of the integration of the dewar to the instrument before launch would be conducted in order to mitigate this possibility. Another single point of failure would be in computer issues used for operations. This would be mitigated via redundancy of computer used to communicate with the satellite.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

A Canadian flagship mission, *Colibrì* will be a demonstration of Canada's leadership in space science and X-ray astronomy. The mission will also support the development of new Canadian technologies in the form of the detectors for *Colibrì*. The *Colibrì* mission is currently in the initial stages and through continued development Canadian capacity in astronomical space missions will increase: building technical expertise, managerial expertise in large space missions and increasing scientific expertise in high-energy astrophysics. Additionally, the training of HQP throughout the mission development will lead to a robust and experienced Canadian workforce in the space sciences.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The *Colibrì* team is comprised of high-energy astrophysicists from across Canada – from seven different universities, indicating a high level of support from the high-energy community within Canada. As the mission continues with its development, and depending on the final mission specifications, other astronomical communities in Canada may be interested in using *Colibrì* to further their research interests: stellar astrophysics may

be able to use *Colibrì* to study stellar magnetic fields, the exoplanet community may be able to use *Colibrì* to study the interaction between close-in exoplanets and their host stars (e.g. photo-evaporation) and planetary community could possibly take advantage of *Colibrì* to study solar system objects in X-rays. At the international level, the initial *Colibrì* concept has been highlighted at various conferences and interest in following the project development has sparked globally. The support needed for the further development of *Colibrì* will help to maintain the reputation Canada has gained for scientific and technological excellence and ingenuity.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

The *Colibrì* mission is currently in the very beginning stages of development, with the concept study on the mission to be completed in early 2020. The *Colibrì* mission requires the support of the LRP in order to continue its development through pre-phase 0 activities such as: STDP, science maturation and mission contribution studies. As well as the in the following phase 0 to through manufacturing activities. Throughout the various development stages of the mission, there will be many opportunities for training HQP and the retention of HQP via staff positions within the mission. The launch of *Colibrì* is expected to occur in the 2030's which will continue the opportunities for HQP in Canada – both through training and retention. LRP's support for *Colibrì* will increase the capacity in Canada for large flagship space missions and will lead to the creation of good middle class jobs in the space sector.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The full detailed costing of the *Colibrì* mission has yet to be completed; we currently estimate a cost of \$500M. The benefits of the investment include: the creation of good jobs in the Canadian space sector through the retention of HQP, innovation in the development of TES detector technology in Canada, which could have applications for other enterprises. Additionally, any investments to the infrastructure, for example the infrastructure for data downlinks from *Colibrì*, will be an asset for any missions which occur beyond the *Colibrì* mission.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

A major programmatic risk would be for the proposed Canadian TES detectors not reaching the required TRL levels. Possible mitigation strategies for this would be to reach out for international partnership, for example NASA-Goddard, for them to join the mission and contribute their detectors to the mission. Additionally, the CSA decides on the funding of studies based on the prioritization in the LRP. In order for this mission to continue its scheduled development it requires the LRP2020 report to rank it as a high priority mission for the high-energy astrophysics community. There is strong community buy-in as noted in box 4.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The *Colibrì* mission offers many benefits to Canadians throughout its development stages and normal operations. Currently, in the early stages of *Colibrì* HQP training has occurred in the form of data simulations and literature reviews. HQP training would continue throughout the development stages with tasks such as assisting in developing a data processing pipeline. During normal operations students and postdocs would get hands on experience in science office activities, preparing them for leading future missions. Through all of its stages, the mission will create jobs, which will retain HQP in Canada with science office staff positions and within

the space sector for infrastructure support. The success of *Colibrì* requires the joint efforts between academia, industry, and government (CSA). Exposing students to the three aforementioned sectors potentially creates new opportunities for trained HQP. An important element of the *Colibrì* mission is developing an outreach plan for interacting with the greater Canadian community sharing the results from the mission and triggering the imaginations of all Canadians.

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